

Fibonacci/Lucas numbers the Kabbalah Tree of Life

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Short Communication

For more than 30 years, Fibonacci has invaded my researcher's life...

After having discovered it in Artificial Intelligence at the heart of the fractal of my artificial neural network Fractal Chaos (Perez, 1988), I have since explored it in the digital structures of DNA sequences.

The role of Fibonacci numbers in the structure of TCAG DNA nucleotides sequences was presented by myself more than 30 years ago (Perez, 1991), (Marcer, 1992), (Stakhov, 2009 pp 111&112), and has since been widely extended (Perez, 1997), (Perez, 2017, 2018), (Perez&Montagnier, 2021).

Also, in order to free myself from the omnipresence of this "Fibonacci mathematical devil", I sometimes distract myself by reading novels...

It was then that, while reading a book on the nationality of Christopher Columbus (Spanish, Portuguese or Italian?), I discovered references to Kabbalah (Dos Santos, 2005).

This was not unknown to me since more than 25 years ago RIP Dominique Aubier, one of the world's greatest pioneers in the numerical decoding of Kabbalah had already asked me about the numbers in DNA (Dominique Aubier

<https://www.dominique-aubier.com/product/les-13-cles-du-code-des-codes/>

And

<https://youtu.be/VDe6pjlPXV0>).

See Kabbalah <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kabbalah>

In Kabbalah the 10 sephiroth are numbered from 1 to 10.

Their spatial arrangement forms the tree of life, a sort of human body.

The left arm of this tree of life (right arm of the symbolic human) is composed from top to bottom of the sephiroths 3 5 and 8.

Symbolic names are :

Binah 3

Geruvah 5

Hod 8

Then, 3 5 8

Here? 3 successive Fibonacci numbers.

What is the probability of such an event?

Number of arrangements of 3 elements among 10 elements = 720

Imagine a race of 10 horses numbered from 1 to 10.

What is the probability that the order of arrival is 3 5 and 8?

1 chance in 720...

3 5 8 fibonacci

Figure 1 - The Tree of Life and the 9 Sephiroths.

Source <https://fr.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Ktreewnames.png>

The human body is often superimposed on the symbolic form of the tree of life. Thus, one can, by analogy, locate there the head, the 2 right and left arms etc...

But a human having two arms, what about the other arm of the tree of life
Is there fibonacci's sister suite, the Lucas suite?

Not exactly when we hoped to find 3 4 7, sorry, we will only find 2 4 7!

As the number 3 has already been used in the Fibonacci sequence 3 5 8 of the first arm, it could therefore not appear in the Lucas sequence 3 4 7 of the other arm.

Amazing though...

When the sum of the codes of the 2 arms is

3 5 8 ==> 16 ==> 7

2 4 7 ==> 13 ==> 4

Lucas again...

FLOWER OF LIFE

Handwritten text in a cursive script, likely a historical or scientific treatise. The text is written in brown ink on aged, stained paper. It is arranged in several lines, with some words appearing to be in a different script or dialect. The text is partially obscured by the circular diagram above it and is difficult to decipher due to the cursive style and fading. The text appears to be a description or explanation of the diagram above it.

3 2 3 7 12 19

$$7 + 12 = 19$$

Evangelist suite (fibonacci+Lucas)

3 2 5 7 12 19 evangelist

2.1.3.4.7. 11 lucas

1 1 2 3 5 8. Fibonacci

The key golden ratio shaded code involved in the Flower of life is the Evangelist suite discovered in brain evolution in our article

<https://www.siftdesk.org/article-details/DUF1220%20Homo%20Sapiens%20and%20Neanderthal%20%20fractal%20periods%20architectures%20breakthrough/184>

And used in negro spiritual songs

And also the resulting adding fibonacci + Lucas suites

Thanks Leonardo da Vinci images sended to me by friend Dr Claudia Krings from Germany I discovered that

3

2

5

7

12

19

Are key numbers of flower of life

See images

Consider adjacent and interfering (overlapping) circles or hexagons

7 circles to make a flower (da Vinci)

3 central column circles

2 side colum circles

5 central adjacent + overlapping circles

But the main discovery is

7 adjacent circles or hexagons

19.total cumulated circles

The 12 overlapping circles

$7 + 12 = 19$

There are the 3key numbers shaded in flower of life

Naturally the ratio between 2 Evangelist numbers is Phii. ie. $19/12$

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